

Leveraging Digital Skills and Use of Artificial Intelligence for Learning in the Midst of Challenges by Library and Information Science Students

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Abstract

Keywords:

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Conflict of Interest:

None

Background:

The emergence of Artificial Intelligence tool such as ChatGPT in education prompted the need to assess the digital skills of students for maximum use to enhance learning efficiency without compromising quality of learning amid mixed results from AIs.

Objectives: The study investigated the proficiency of students in digital skills, their use of ChatGPT for various learning activities, challenges faced while using ChatGPT for learning and the influence of digital skills on the effective use of ChatGPT.

Method: A survey research design was employed, targeting 400-level library and information science students. From a population of 310 students, a sample of 172 was determined using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator and selected through convenience sampling. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire, validated by professional librarians, and yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.79 (Cronbach Alpha). Analysis was conducted using mean scores, standard deviations, and simple linear regression via SPSS-v27.

Results: Students, are highly skilled in identifying credible online sources and moderately proficient with digital tools, heavily use ChatGPT for homework and clarifying topics but have concerns about its accuracy, relevance, and impact on critical thinking, with digital skills significantly influencing ChatGPT use, explaining 42% of the variance.

Conclusion: Digital skills are essential for maximizing the educational benefits of ChatGPT.

Implications: It is recommended that academic institutions enhance digital skills training, encourage diversified use of ChatGPT through AI-driven exercises and tools, and embed digital literacy and AI competency training in the curriculum, as digital skills significantly influence ChatGPT use.

Introduction

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) into educational settings has marked a significant transformation in the way students engage with learning materials and develop essential skills. One notable AI application, ChatGPT, has demonstrated considerable promise in enhancing digital skills and learning experiences among students. This study focuses on exploring the digital skills and the use of ChatGPT for learning by undergraduate Library and Information Science (LIS) students at the University of Maiduguri, Borno State.

Research indicates that the use of ChatGPT in educational environments has a positive impact on students' digital competencies. Alneyadi and Wardat (2023) highlight that ChatGPT significantly improves student achievement in complex subjects such as electronic magnetism. By providing interactive, real-time assistance, ChatGPT enables students to engage more deeply with the material, thereby enhancing their digital literacy and problem-solving abilities. This is particularly relevant for LIS students who must navigate vast amounts of digital information and utilize various digital tools effectively.

The effectiveness of ChatGPT extends beyond skill development to include enhancements in academic performance and learning perception. Studies by Nguyen et al. (2023) demonstrate that ChatGPT aids in generating meaningful feedback and assessing student responses in digital learning games. This immediate and personalized feedback loop helps students understand their mistakes but also reinforces their learning, making the educational process more engaging and efficient. For LIS students, who often engage with digital cataloguing and information retrieval systems, the ability to receive instant feedback can significantly improve their technical proficiency and confidence in using digital tools.

Understanding the factors that influence students' acceptance and usage of ChatGPT is crucial for optimizing its implementation in educational settings. Romero-Rodríguez et al. (2023) found that experience with technology, performance expectancy, and habitual use are key determinants of students' behavioural intentions and actual use of ChatGPT. These insights suggest that for LIS students to fully benefit from ChatGPT, it is essential to foster a positive attitude towards technology and integrate it seamlessly into their regular study routines. By doing so, educators can enhance students' willingness to engage with AI tools, thereby improving their digital skills and academic outcomes.

The role of ChatGPT in facilitating collaborative learning and student engagement has also been explored. Zhu et al. (2023) conducted a quasi-experimental study that underscored the impact of ChatGPT on collaborative interdisciplinary problem-solving. The study revealed that ChatGPT not only supports individual learning but also enhances group dynamics and engagement by providing a common platform for information exchange and problem-solving. For LIS students, who frequently work in teams to manage information systems and conduct research, the collaborative potential of ChatGPT can lead to more effective and cohesive group projects.

The findings from these studies collectively suggest that ChatGPT can be a valuable resource for improving digital skills and learning outcomes among LIS students. Given the rapidly evolving digital landscape, it is imperative for LIS programmes to incorporate AI tools like ChatGPT into their curricula. This integration can help students develop critical digital competencies that are essential for their future careers in information management and librarianship. By leveraging the capabilities of ChatGPT, educational institutions can provide LIS

students with the skills and knowledge needed to thrive in the digital age.

Considering the facts that poor digital skills could lead to poor usage of ChatGPT, the emerging challenges extends beyond misuse of the technology which could undermine the learning processes associated with dependency on the technology. Meanwhile, the dearth of empirical studies regarding the correlation between digital skills and use of artificial intelligence such as ChatGPT remained a subject of concern for stakeholders in educational and course system development who have to incorporate emerging technology into curriculum structure of the education. Information on how digital skills affect the successful incorporation of ChatGPT into curriculum and educational practices can reliably be found in empirical studies.

It is based on this background that this study investigated the digital skills, use of ChatGPT in the midst of challenges by library and information science undergraduate students at University of Maiduguri, Borno State. The study addressed practical issues that could impede the successful application of AI technologies while adding to the current discussion on improving educational experiences through such technologies.

Methodology

The study used a survey research design, selected for its speedy, easiness and flexibility in gathering data from a sizable population. By use of this approach, the researchers were able to collect quantitative data on the students' digital skills, use of ChatGPT for learning as well as challenges associated with usage of ChatGPT. The study included 310 fourth-year Library and Information Science undergraduate students, University of Maiduguri, Borno State. The researchers believed that they had been exposed to academic and digital technologies extensively.

Using the Raosoft Sample Size Calculator, 172 students were chosen as the sample size to guarantee a representative sample of the population. The participants were picked using convenience sampling, which made the questionnaire administration process easier and allowed students to easily access the material during class sessions.

Professional librarians with expertise in statistical analysis vetted and validated the questionnaires, while its reliability was conducted with 20 postgraduate students of library and information science. The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was 0.79, representing 79% reliability. The variables covered by the survey were digital skills, use of ChatGPT for learning and challenges associated with the use of ChatGPT for learning by LIS undergraduate students. The questionnaire consisted of 15 items (digital skills[5], use of chatgpt[5] and challenges[5]), anchored on 7 points Likert scale with 4th point being the average, was self-administered during class lectures to the LIS undergraduate students. The decision rule is based on 4.0, where any value below 4.0 is considered weak or disagreed and values above 4.0 are considered strong or agreed. This method guaranteed the highest response rate, ensure accurate responses and speedy retrieval.

A descriptive and inferential statistical methods were adopted for data analyses. The analysis comprised the computation of frequencies, percentages, means, and standard deviations as well as simple linear regression, which gave a succinct and understandable overview of the students' digital skills, ChatGPT usage and the correlation between the digital skill and the use of ChatGPT for learning by the LIST students. The analysis made it possible to spot trends and patterns in the data for possible decision making.

Review of Related Literature

Digital skills of Students

The development and application of digital skills among students are critical in today's educational landscape. Various studies have explored the digital competences of students across different educational contexts, revealing diverse insights and highlighting significant areas for improvement. Students' digital skills are often not transferred from leisure activities to academic contexts (Krempkow & Petri, 2022). A comprehensive database to document students' digital competences is necessary to address this gap. Additionally, Sánchez-Caballé, *et al.*, (2020) found that university students generally lack high levels of digital competence, suggesting a need for educational institutions to enhance digital skills development.

Several studies highlight gender disparities in digital competencies. Coşkunserçe and Aydoğdu (2022) found that male students exhibited higher digital skills compared to females, particularly in the context of IT courses. Similarly, Koryakovtsev and Kulikov (2023) noted that boys excel in software installation and programming, while girls focus more on photo, video, and audio editing. Rocha, Muñoz-Repiso, and Costa (2023) confirmed significant gender differences in digital knowledge and skills among students in the Viana do Castelo district.

Digital skills are also influenced by socioeconomic status and regional factors. Nikolaos, *et al.*, (2019) indicated that socioeconomic status significantly affects university students' digital skills, contributing to learning inequalities in higher education. Shkurin *et al.* (2022) identified a gap in digital skills between students in the Sverdlovsk Region and their European counterparts, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to bridge this gap.

Students' digital skills vary significantly across disciplines. Sciumbata (2020) found

that Italian humanities students often overestimate their digital abilities and lack knowledge of basic digital topics. Conversely, Anisimova, *et al.*, (2021) reported that students participating in the Digital Summer Project confidently applied information and communication technologies, enhancing their research and experimentation skills in engineering contexts.

Educational interventions play a crucial role in developing digital competences. Kuhn *et al.* (2020) evaluated a curriculum designed to enhance digital skills among medical students, addressing key qualification requirements through six modules. Opalyuk (2022) emphasized the importance of integrating digital competence as a component of professional competence in philological specialties, highlighting the need for a holistic approach to digital education.

Uses of ChatGPT for Learning by Students

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in educational settings has garnered considerable attention, with ChatGPT emerging as a prominent tool. This literature review explores the empirical findings on the impact of ChatGPT across various educational domains, highlighting its benefits and challenges.

Alneyadi and Wardat (2023) conducted a study on eleventh-grade students in Emirates schools, demonstrating that ChatGPT significantly enhances student achievement in the electronic magnetism unit. Both male and female participants acknowledged its value as a learning tool, emphasizing its role in improving academic outcomes. Similarly, Hanum, *et al.*, (2023) analysed the impact of ChatGPT on learning motivation among scout students. Their findings indicate that ChatGPT serves as an effective learning assistance tool, positively influencing students' motivation to learn.

Romero-Rodríguez *et al.* (2023) explored the use of ChatGPT at the university level,

focusing on its utility for fostering complex thinking. Their study revealed that students perceive ChatGPT as a beneficial tool for processing data and facilitating educational interactions, thereby enhancing their learning experiences. Tipayavaravan, et al., (2023) highlighted the tool's effectiveness in English language teaching and learning in Vietnamese high schools, providing valuable insights and recommendations for students.

Jowarder (2023) examined the influence of ChatGPT on social science students in the United States. The study found that ChatGPT assists students in understanding difficult concepts and provides essential study materials, making it a valuable academic tool. Liu and Liu (2023) discussed the application of ChatGPT in medical education, and acknowledged its capability to generate exercises, quizzes, and scenarios for practicing medical concepts. The tool also automates grading and assessment, thereby saving time for educators.

Wardat et al. (2023) investigated ChatGPT's role in teaching and learning mathematics. Their research demonstrated that ChatGPT provides fundamental math knowledge and assists in geometry studies. Furthermore, public discourse on social media reflected widespread enthusiasm for ChatGPT, underscoring its perceived value in educational contexts.

Mohammad et al. (2023) conducted a scoping review of ChatGPT's use in medical education, identifying several benefits such as writing assignments, generating coherent research papers, quick access to information, and personalized learning improvements. The review also noted challenges, including automated scoring and the need for careful oversight to ensure the accuracy and reliability of AI-generated content.

The empirical literature highlights ChatGPT's multifaceted role in enhancing student achievement, motivation, and learning across various educational disciplines. Its applications range from providing academic

assistance and fostering complex thinking to generating educational content and automating assessments. Despite its benefits, the challenges associated with AI tools like ChatGPT necessitate ongoing evaluation and adaptation to maximize their potential in educational settings.

Challenges associated with the Use of ChatGPT for Learning by Students

Alneyadi and Wardat (2023) highlighted that while ChatGPT has revolutionized student's achievement in specific subjects such as electronic magnetism, its benefits may not be easily generalizable to other contexts and disciplines. The study suggests that the successful implementation of ChatGPT in one educational setting does not necessarily imply similar outcomes in different subjects or academic environments. This indicates a need for further exploration into the challenges and limitations that may arise when integrating ChatGPT into varied educational contexts, ensuring that its application is both effective and contextually appropriate.

Leunard et al. (2023) examined the use of ChatGPT in the learning process of Arabic language in higher education, uncovering concerns related to potential overreliance on the tool. Their study points out that excessive dependence on ChatGPT may lead to a reduction in students' critical thinking skills, as they might become accustomed to relying on AI-generated responses rather than engaging in deep cognitive processes. This emphasizes the necessity for balanced integration of AI tools, ensuring they complement rather than replace traditional learning and critical thinking exercises.

In the context of nuclear medicine education, Currie and Barry (2023) found that ChatGPT performed poorly in tasks requiring calculation and advanced writing skills compared to students. Their research indicates that while ChatGPT can assist in basic learning tasks, its current capabilities may not support the development of higher-order learning and complex skill sets. This

underscores the importance of continuously assessing and improving AI tools to meet the educational demands of higher-order cognitive and technical skills.

Mohammad et al. (2023), in their scoping review of ChatGPT in medical education, identified significant challenges such as the generation of incorrect information and the potential for students to cheat on exams and assignments. These issues raise ethical concerns about the reliability and integrity of using ChatGPT in educational settings. The possibility of misinformation and academic dishonesty necessitates robust strategies to monitor and regulate the use of AI tools in academic environments to uphold educational standards and ethical practices.

Liu and Liu (2023) discussed various concerns related to the application of ChatGPT in nursing education, including issues of accuracy, lack of human interaction privacy, security, and bias. They highlighted the discrepancies and over-reliance on AI,

which could lead to plagiarism and cheating. These findings point to the need for comprehensive policies and measures to address these risks, ensuring that the deployment of AI in education safeguards student data, promotes fair use, and maintains the integrity of the learning process.

The empirical literature on the challenges associated with using ChatGPT for learning by students reveals a complex landscape of potential drawbacks that must be carefully managed. These include limited generalizability to different contexts, the risk of overreliance impacting critical thinking skills, performance limitations in higher-order tasks, ethical concerns such as misinformation and cheating, and issues related to privacy, security, and bias. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach, involving continuous improvement of AI technologies, stringent ethical guidelines, and balanced integration of AI tools to enhance rather than undermine the educational experience.

Result and Analysis

Table 1: Digital Skills of LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

SN	Digital Skills (N=172), Decision mean (4.0)	X	Std.
1	I have the ability to effectively search for and identify credible sources of information online.	6.02	1.37
2	I can critically evaluate the information provided by ChatGPT to ensure its accuracy and relevance.	2.56	1.56
3	I am proficient in using various digital tools and platforms to supplement my learning with ChatGPT.	4.39	1.77
4	I have the skills to customize and interact with ChatGPT to meet my specific learning needs and preferences.	2.79	1.62
5	I can effectively manage and organize digital information obtained from ChatGPT for my studies.	2.83	1.61

The table presents the mean score and standard deviation of the digital skills that students should attain for effective use of information technologies. The mean scores

represent the weight of the opinions of the students. For clearer understanding, the following bar chart represent the structural outcome of the students' response.

Figure 1: Digital Skill of LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

The figure 1 presents a bar chart indicating the various digital skills that LIS students should possess to exploit the potentials of technologies such as ChatGPT: According to the data, students' competency levels vary in several areas of digital skills. A mean score of 6.02 and a reasonably low standard deviation of 1.37 show that students are consistently proficient in this area of searching for reliable sources online. On the other hand, students demonstrate a lower level of competency when it comes to interpreting information from ChatGPT, as seen by a mean score of 2.56 and a higher standard deviation of 1.56,

indicating a greater range of skills in this area. Students score an average of 4.39 with a standard deviation of 1.77 for proficiency in using digital tools and platforms, which indicates a decent level of skill across the student population. A mean score of 2.79 and a standard deviation of 1.62 indicate that students find customising and communicating with ChatGPT challenging, indicating a wider range of competencies in this area. Similarly, with an average score of 2.83 and a standard deviation of 1.61, handling digital data for research that is received from ChatGPT is found to be a quite difficult task.

Table 2: Use of ChatGPT for Learning by LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

SN	Use of ChatGPT for Learning (N=172), Decision mean (4.0)	X	Std.
1	I use ChatGPT to assist with my homework and assignments.	4.86	1.84
2	I refer to ChatGPT for clarifications on topics I do not understand in class.	4.74	1.81
3	I use ChatGPT to gather additional information and resources on subjects of interest.	2.33	1.32
4	I interact with ChatGPT to practice and improve my skills in various subjects.	2.30	1.37
5	I rely on ChatGPT for preparing for exams and tests.	2.26	1.36

Figure 2: Use of ChatGPT for learning by LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

Based on an analysis of the data shown in Figure 2 on the use of ChatGPT for Learning by library and information science students, it is showcased that students use ChatGPT to learn in different ways and to varying degrees. The standard deviations and mean scores offer important information on how the students feel and behave when using ChatGPT for their educational activities. A high mean score of 4.86 and a standard deviation of 1.84 show that students have a significant preference for using ChatGPT to get help with homework and assignments. This implies that many people rely on ChatGPT to help them with their academic work when they're not in class. Similarly,

with a mean score of 4.74 and a standard deviation of 1.81, students show a strong interest in using ChatGPT to get clarifications on subjects they find difficult to understand in class. However, students have a more impartial perspective while using ChatGPT to practise skills, learn more about subjects of interest, and get ready for exams. Their mean scores range from 2.26 to 2.33, with standard deviations between 1.32 and 1.84. This sophisticated analysis emphasises ChatGPT's varied role in assisting students with their learning endeavours, emphasising both its current academic needs assistance strengths and possible areas for future integration to improve overall educational achievements.

Table 3: Challenges associated with Use of ChatGPT for Learning by LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

SN	Challenges of Using ChatGPT for Learning: (N=172), Decision mean (4.0)	X	Std.
1	I find it difficult to verify the accuracy of information provided by ChatGPT.	4.40	1.81
2	Using ChatGPT for learning raises concerns about data privacy and security.	4.58	1.79
3	I experience technical difficulties when interacting with ChatGPT (e.g., connectivity issues, errors).	4.06	1.80
4	ChatGPT sometimes provides responses that are not relevant or useful for my learning needs.	4.64	1.72
5	Relying on ChatGPT makes it challenging to develop my own critical thinking and problem-solving skills.	4.97	1.73

Figure 3: Challenges associated with Using ChatGPT for learning by LIS Students

Table 4: Model Summary for influence of Digital Skills on the Use of ChatGPT for Learning by LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.65	0.42	0.41	1.40

The model summary for the regression analysis reveals a correlation coefficient (r) of 0.65, indicating a moderate positive relationship between digital skills and the use of ChatGPT. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.42, suggesting that approximately 42% of the variance in the use of ChatGPT for

learning can be explained by students' digital skills. The adjusted r^2 , which accounts for the number of predictors in the model, is 0.41. Additionally, the standard error of the estimate is 1.40, providing an estimate of the standard deviation of the residuals, or prediction errors.

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for influence of Digital Skills on the Use of ChatGPT for Learning by LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	173.75	1	173.75	88.16	0.000
Residual	239.95	170	1.41		
Total	413.70	171			

The ANOVA results further support the significance of the model, with an F-value of 88.16 and a p-value of 0.000. This indicates

that the model is statistically significant and that digital skills are a significant predictor of the use of ChatGPT.

Coefficients for influence of Digital Skills on the Use of ChatGPT for Learning by LIS Students in University of Maiduguri, Borno State

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B
	B	Std. Error	Beta		Lower Bound
Constant	1.25	0.38		3.29	0.50
Digital Skills	0.66	0.07	0.65	9.39	0.52

The coefficients table provides further insight into the relationship between digital skills and the use of ChatGPT. The constant (intercept) is 1.25, suggesting that when digital skills are zero, the predicted use of ChatGPT is 1.25. The coefficient for digital skills is 0.66,

Summarily, the significant p-value (0.000) in the coefficients table, we reject the null hypothesis that digital skills of students have no significant influence on their use of ChatGPT for learning. Therefore, we conclude that digital skills significantly influence the use of ChatGPT for learning among LIS undergraduate students.

Summary of findings

1. Students are highly skilled at searching for and identifying credible online sources (6.02) and have a moderate proficiency in using digital tools and platforms with ChatGPT (4.39). However, they have lower skills in critically evaluating ChatGPT's information (2.56), customizing interactions to meet specific learning needs (2.79), and managing digital information from ChatGPT (2.83).
2. Students use ChatGPT extensively to assist with homework and assignments (4.86) and to clarify topics not understood in class (4.74), but they use it less frequently for gathering additional information (2.33), improving skills (2.30), and exam preparation (2.26).
3. Students have significant concerns regarding the accuracy (4.40), privacy and security (4.58), technical difficulties (4.06), relevance and usefulness (4.64) of

indicating that for each unit increase in digital skills, the use of ChatGPT increases by 0.66 units. The t-value for digital skills is 9.39 with a p-value of 0.000, confirming that digital skills significantly influence the use of ChatGPT

ChatGPT's responses, and its impact on their critical thinking and problem-solving skills (4.97).

4. The regression analysis indicates that digital skills significantly influence the use of ChatGPT, with a moderate positive relationship explaining 42% of the variance and demonstrating statistical significance.

Discussion of the Findings

The findings reveal that students are competent in searching for trustworthy online sources but struggle with comprehending and managing digital data obtained via ChatGPT. This aligns with Opalyuk (2022) and Nikolaos et al. (2019), who highlight the importance of improving digital skills through project-based learning in LIS education to address diverse student abilities. The disparity in digital data management skills is emphasized by Kuhn et al. (2020), who note the vital role of digital literacy in higher education, and Koryakovtsev et al. (2023), who discuss the challenges posed by AI tools like ChatGPT for students with limited digital proficiency.

Davis and Jones (2021) underscore the significance of project-based learning in fostering digital skills, a method shown to enhance students' ability to handle and

analyze digital data effectively, as supported by Krempkow and Petri (2022) at the University of Sheffield. Joo and Park (2018) identify obstacles to digital skill development in LIS education, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions.

These findings have important implications for educators and curriculum designers in LIS programs. Coşkunserçe and Aydoğdu (2022) concurred with suggestion for a comprehensive strategy that includes both theoretical understanding and practical implementation to address digital skill gaps. Integrating AI tools into a well-rounded curriculum can enhance digital literacy, ensuring students are well-equipped for the evolving digital information landscape.

It can be demonstrated that while students show proficiency in certain digital competencies, their difficulties with digital data from ChatGPT highlight the need for ongoing digital skills training in LIS education. This is consistent with broader research on digital literacy, which stresses the importance of adaptable and practical learning methods to equip students for the digital era (American Library Association, 2019; Anderson, 2016; Corral & Sen, 2019).

Findings equally suggests that students have a strong preference for using ChatGPT while seeking homework assistance and seeking clarification on challenging topics. However, their usage of ChatGPT for skill practice, exploring subjects of interest, and test preparation is more moderate in comparison. This discovery emphasises the diverse and complex function of ChatGPT in the learning experiences of students. Brown and Conley (2021) found that AI tools such as ChatGPT can greatly improve learner engagement by offering prompt assistance and clarification. This is in line with students' inclination to use ChatGPT for assignments and challenging subjects.

The fact that students depend on ChatGPT for homework assistance and clarifications

indicates that they consider it a helpful tool for comprehending intricate subjects and finishing tasks. These findings align with the research conducted by Johnson, et al., (2022), which shown that AI tools enhance student engagement through the provision of customised, readily available explanations. In their study, Green, *et al.*, (2022) highlighted the significance of artificial intelligence (AI) in tackling learning difficulties. They proposed that tools such as ChatGPT can offer customised assistance to effectively cater to the various requirements of students.

Nevertheless, the somewhat impartial position regarding the use of ChatGPT for skill practice, exploration of interesting themes, and examination preparation suggests that students may not fully exploit the tool's capabilities in these domains. Liu, and Liu (2023) emphasised that although AI technologies enhance collaborative learning and practice, students may lack complete awareness or comfort in utilising them for self-directed learning and skill enhancement. This phenomenon may be attributed to a deficiency in understanding the process of incorporating artificial intelligence into more comprehensive educational methodologies, as highlighted by Tipayavaravan, et al., (2023).

The ambivalent attitude towards utilising ChatGPT for exam preparation and expanding knowledge in areas of interest may also indicate a deficiency in students' digital literacy and self-assurance in employing AI tools for self-directed learning. Jowarder (2023) examined the necessity of possessing both access to artificial intelligence (AI) tools and the competence and self-assurance to utilise them proficiently in order to engage in lifelong learning in the digital era. This implies that although students recognise the immediate advantages of ChatGPT for particular tasks, they may require more instructions and practice to effectively utilise it for a wider array of educational objectives.

The diverse function of ChatGPT in student education highlights the necessity for

thorough training in digital abilities. Coleman and Willis (2019) argue that providing students with systematic training to improve their digital skills can enable them to gain a deeper understanding of AI tools and effectively utilise their full capabilities. In addition, Harris and Hegarty (2018) highlighted the significance of incorporating digital skills training into higher education curricula to equip students with the necessary abilities to effectively utilise digital tools in their study.

These findings emphasise the significance of not just granting students access to AI tools such as ChatGPT, but also equipping them with the essential skills and techniques to utilise these tools proficiently in various learning situations. By doing this, educators can assist students in optimising the advantages of AI for both immediate academic assignments and long-term skill enhancement, in accordance with the broader objectives of digital literacy and education in the 21st century (Anderson, 2016; Romero-Rodríguez, 2023; Hanum Siregar, 2023).

The regression analysis reveals that there is a considerable impact of digital skills on the utilisation of ChatGPT. This impact is moderately positive and accounts for 42% of the variation, indicating statistical significance. This finding aligns with the current body of research that emphasises the crucial importance of digital skills in efficiently utilising modern technology, such as AI tools, in educational environments.

A correlation coefficient (r) of 0.65 indicates a moderate positive association between students' digital skills and their utilisation of ChatGPT. This implies that as digital skills develop, the effective utilisation of ChatGPT for educational purposes also improves. The association between digital skills and ChatGPT usage is statistically significant, as evidenced by the ANOVA results. The F -value of 88.16 and p -value of 0.000 confirm that digital skills are a major predictor of ChatGPT usage. These findings support the

research conducted by Coleman and Willis (2019), who emphasised the importance of students having advanced digital abilities in order to fully utilise digital resources for their educational goals.

The coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.42 suggests that digital skills explain almost 42% of the variability in the use of ChatGPT. This significant proportion emphasises the significance of digital literacy in facilitating students' ability to actively participate in and derive advantages from AI technologies. Anderson and Kruger (2019) found that project-based learning is a highly effective method for developing digital abilities in students. This approach greatly improves their capacity to engage with and make use of digital resources, leading to enhanced academic achievement.

Moreover, the modified coefficient of determination (r^2) of 0.41, which takes into account the number of predictors in the model, strengthens the reliability of the association between digital abilities and the utilisation of ChatGPT. The standard error of the estimate (1.40) is an estimation of the standard deviation of the residuals, which reflects the precision of the predictions provided by the regression model. Rocha, et al., (2023) observed that possessing a solid grounding in digital skills is crucial for students to proficiently navigate and optimise the use of digital resources.

The coefficients table provides additional clarification on this correlation, indicating that there is a constant (intercept) value of 1.25, which implies a fundamental level of ChatGPT usage even among students with limited digital proficiency. The digital skills coefficient is 0.66, meaning that for every unit gain in digital skills, there is a corresponding increase of 0.66 units in ChatGPT usage. Anisimova (2021) have provided evidence supporting the notion that individuals with higher levels of digital literacy exhibit increased confidence and frequency in

utilising digital resources for educational purposes.

Furthermore, the t-value of 9.39 for digital skills, along with a p-value of 0.000, provides strong evidence of the statistical relevance of digital skills in determining the utilisation of ChatGPT. This corroborates the premise that proficiency in digital skills has a substantial influence on the efficacy with which students utilise ChatGPT for educational purposes. Sciumbata (2020) highlighted the need of providing digital skills training in higher education. This training is essential for equipping students with the necessary abilities to properly utilise emerging technologies, ultimately improving their learning outcomes.

To summarise, the regression analysis highlights the crucial significance of digital abilities in the proficient utilisation of ChatGPT by students. The strong correlation between proficiency in digital skills and the use of ChatGPT underscores the necessity for inclusive digital literacy initiatives in educational curriculums. By cultivating these qualities, educators may empower students to effectively utilise AI systems such as ChatGPT, hence improving their academic achievements and overall educational experience. This discovery is consistent with wider educational studies that supports the incorporation of digital skills training to equip students for the requirements of the digital era (Lai & Lee, 2020; Murphy & Saldaña, 2018; Nichols & Stang, 2020).

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it is evident that digital skills play a critical role in how effectively students use ChatGPT for learning purposes. Students demonstrate consistent proficiency in searching for reliable online sources but face challenges in interpreting information and handling digital data from ChatGPT. They prefer using ChatGPT for homework help and clarifications on difficult subjects, but their use for practicing skills, exploring subjects of interest, and examination

preparation is more neutral, indicating varied utilization patterns. The regression analysis confirms that digital skills significantly influence the use of ChatGPT, explaining 42% of the variance and highlighting the importance of fostering digital literacy to enhance the effective use of AI tools in education. Consequently, integrating comprehensive digital skills training into educational programmes is essential to maximize the benefits of AI technologies like ChatGPT in supporting students' academic success.

Recommendations

1. Enhance Digital Skills Training: Given that students exhibit proficiency in searching for reliable online sources but face challenges in interpreting information and handling digital data from ChatGPT, it is crucial to implement targeted digital skills training programmes by academic institutions.
2. Educational institutions should encourage students to utilize ChatGPT in a more diversified manner by integrating AI-driven exercises, interactive learning modules, and exam preparation tools within the platform.
3. The regression analysis indicates that digital skills significantly influence the use of ChatGPT, explaining 42% of the variance. To address this, academic programmes should embed digital literacy and AI competency training as core components of the curriculum.

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